

STUDY OF POLYMERIC NANO-COMPOSITES WITH CARBON NANOTUBES

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ABSTRACT: The reinforcing effect of carbon nanotubes in a polypropylene matrix have been investigated using molecular dynamic simulations. Simulations have been performed on an amorphous polypropylene system containing an infinite carbon nanotube and a finite, capped carbon nanotube, respectively. For the infinite carbon nanotube/polypropylene system the tensile modulus was identical to the upper bound of the modulus given by the Voigt approximation. For the finite, capped carbon nanotube/polypropylene system no reinforcing effect was observed due to the short length of the tube and the reduced load transfer between the matrix and the nanotube.

KEYWORDS: Molecular dynamics, nanocomposites, carbon nanotubes.

INTRODUCTION

Ever since the discovery of the carbon nanotubes [1] these nanoscale carbon structures have attracted a considerably research interest. The immense interest is mainly due to the promising optical, electronic, thermal and mechanical properties and the size of the nanotubes. The intense research in the field has resulted in a broad range of proposed applications which covers the use of carbon nanotubes in e.g. field emission displays [2], nanodevices such as molecular bearings [3], nanocircuits [4] and nanocomposites which is the subject of this paper.

A carbon nanotube can be considered as a sheet of hexagonal arranged carbon atoms that have been rolled into a tube as shown in figure 1. The nanotube can either be capped at the ends with a carbon hemisphere or can have open ends. Two types of carbon nanotubes exist: the single walled carbon nanotubes which consist of a single tube and the multi walled carbon nanotubes which consist of several concentric tubes.

Figure 1: Single walled carbon nanotube with open ends

The mechanical properties of the carbon nanotubes have been the subject of numerous experimental and computational studies. Examples of the experimental studies have been shown by e.g. Treacy et.al. [5]

who estimated the Young's modulus of the nanotubes by use of thermal induced vibrations and obtained an average Young's modulus of 1,8 TPa. Wong et.al. [6] used the tip of an atomic force microscope to bend nanotubes while registering the deflection and the force exerted. The group obtained a Young's modulus with a mean value of 1,28 TPa. The Young's modulus of carbon nanotubes have also been studied using computational methods such as ab initio calculations and molecular dynamics simulations. Sánchez-Portal et.al. [7] studied the elastic properties of nanotubes using ab initio calculations and obtained a Young's modulus close to 1 TPa. An example on the use of molecular dynamic simulations to determine the response of a nanotube was presented by Zhou and Shi [8] who applied molecular dynamics to simulate the tensile properties of carbon nanotubes with and without hydrogen inside. Their simulations yielded a Young's modulus about 750 GPa. The strength of the nanotubes has also been examined in several studies. One example is Yu et.al [9] who investigated the tensile strength of multi walled carbon nanotubes and found that the strength of the tubes used in the experiments ranged between 11 Gpa - 63 GPa.

Even though there are large variations in the values obtained for the mechanical properties of the carbon nanotubes the results are promising and hence there is great interest in using the tubes in structural applications. One application in which the mechanical properties of the nanotubes can be utilized is as the reinforcing phase in a nanotube/polymer composite.

A number of experimental studies have examined the use of carbon nanotubes in different composites and the resulting properties of the composite. For example, Schadler et.al. [10] and Gong et.al. [11] have studied carbon nanotube/epoxy composites. Schadler et.al. [10] tested composites with a 5 wt% content of nanotubes in both tension and compression and observed a 20 % and 24 % increase in tensile and compression modulus, respectively. Gong et.al. [11] tested composites with surfactant treated carbon nanotubes. With 1 wt% content of nanotubes the tensile modulus was increased by more than 30 %. Other studies have examined the effect of mixing carbon nanotubes in a poly(methyl methacrylate) matrix. Haggemueller et.al. [12] investigated poly(methyl methacrylate) fibers with a varying content of single walled carbon nanotubes. They observed an increase in both the elastic modulus and the yield stress with an increase in the amount of nanotubes. With an 8 wt% content of nanotubes the elastic modulus almost doubled. Cooper et.al. [13] have investigated carbon nanotube/ poly(methyl methacrylate) composites containing both single and multi walled nanotubes. Their results indicated that the tensile modulus of the composite was almost insensitive to the presence of the nanotubes but that the impact strength was improved significantly. Shaffer and Windle [14] studied carbon nanotube/ poly(vinyl alcohol) composite film and observed that the presence of the nanotubes stiffens the material, especially at high temperatures. Qian et.al. [15] have produced multi walled carbon nanotube/polystyrene composite films with 1 wt% content of nanotubes. The elastic modulus was increased 36 % - 42 % and the strength was increased ~ 25 % by the addition of the tubes. Polypropylene fibers reinforced with nanotubes have been studied by Kearns and Shambaugh [16] who observed an increase in the tensile strength and modulus of 40 % and 55 %, respectively, by the addition of 1 wt% of single walled carbon nanotubes. Most of the above examples show that addition of even a small amount of carbon nanotubes can enhance the mechanical properties of the material. To obtain an understanding of the mechanisms on a molecular level studies of nanotube/polymer composites have been performed using molecular dynamics simulations. Lordi and Yao [17] have studied the binding energies and sliding frictional stresses between carbon nanotubes and various polymeric materials. They reported that the strength of the interface between the nanotube and the polymers is only slightly dependent on these properties and that the conformations of the polymers were more essential. Frankland and Brenner [18] have investigated the behavior of an infinite and a finite single walled carbon nanotube embedded in a polyethylene matrix while Frankland et.al. [19] have investigated the influence of chemical cross-links between a single

walled nanotube and an amorphous and crystalline polyethylene matrix, respectively. They observed that for a small amount of cross-links the load transfer between the nanotube and the matrix was improved considerably.

In this paper the results of two preliminary molecular dynamic simulations of an infinite and a finite single walled carbon nanotube embedded in an amorphous polypropylene matrix is reported. The simulations are part of a computational and experimental study of carbon nanotube/polypropylene nanocomposites and the aim of the simulations are to model the reinforcing effect of the nanotube on the amorphous polypropylene matrix.

MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATIONS

Two systems have been modeled using molecular dynamics simulations: a system consisting of an infinite carbon nanotube embedded in an amorphous polypropylene matrix and a system composed of a finite and capped nanotube, also in an amorphous polypropylene matrix.

In both systems the amorphous polypropylene matrix has been represented by 30 polymer chains with 40 repeat units in each and a total number of atoms of 10860. Both of the systems were modeled by applying periodic boundary conditions on the cells. In the case of the infinite nanotube/polypropylene composite the carbon nanotube was modeled as a single walled nanotube having a diameter of 0,7 nm. The nanotube extends the entire cell and as a result of the periodic boundary conditions the tube is modeled as an infinite tube. The cell containing the infinite nanotube and the polypropylene matrix has a total number of atoms of 11112 and has the approximate dimensions 3x6x6 nm after equilibration. In the case of the finite and capped nanotube the tube was modeled as a 0,7 nm in diameter single walled carbon nanotube with a length ~ 5 nm and consisting of 456 carbon atoms. The cell containing the finite nanotube and the polypropylene matrix had the dimensions ~ 3x7x5 nm after equilibration. In both of the systems no primary bonding between the nanotube and the polymer matrix was modeled and hence only weak secondary bonding was considered. The two systems are shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Molecular models of the infinite and the finite nanotube/polypropylene composites

For comparison two other systems has been modeled: a system containing only the infinite single walled carbon nanotube used in the simulation described above and a system containing only the amorphous polypropylene matrix.

The molecular dynamic simulations were performed using Materials Studio [20] with the Condensed-phase Optimized Molecular Potentials for Atomistic Simulation Studies (COMPASS) force field [20,21]. The COMPASS force field is parameterized for the most common organic and inorganic small molecules and for polymers and is based on the Polymer Consistent Force Field used by Lordi and Yao [17] in their study of carbon nanotube/polymer composites.

The initial molecular structure of the amorphous polypropylene matrix was generated using Amorphous Cell [20] followed by an energy minimization in order to remove close contacts between the atoms. The Amorphous Cell program randomly generates the coordinates of the atoms in the polymer chains using a modified Markov process. After generation the polypropylene matrix was equilibrated through a number of molecular dynamics runs of a total length of ~ 100 ps. The equilibration procedure constructed a polypropylene matrix with a density of $0,89 \text{ g/cm}^3$ which is slightly more than the $0,85 \text{ g/cm}^3$ reported for an amorphous polypropylene [22].

The total system consisting of nanotube and polypropylene was then further equilibrated for 20 ps in order to obtain a stress free initial state. After the equilibration runs tensile stress was applied in steps for periods of 5 ps in the longitudinal direction of the carbon nanotube and data was collected. All of the molecular dynamics simulations were performed with a time step of 1 fs and at a temperature of 300 K.

RESULTS

In figure 3 the longitudinal stress-strain diagram for the infinite carbon nanotube/polypropylene composite is shown. For comparison molecular dynamic simulations have also been conducted on an amorphous polypropylene and on a single walled carbon nanotube and the results of these simulations are also plotted.

Figure 3: Stress-strain diagram for the infinite carbon nanotube/polypropylene nanocomposite, the polypropylene system and the single walled carbon nanotube.

From the stress-strain plots the tensile modulus can be determined for the infinite nanotube/polypropylene composite and for the polypropylene system and the nanotube. The moduli of the polypropylene system and of the carbon nanotube can be used to determine the upper bound of the tensile modulus of the nanocomposite using the volume fraction of the nanotube and the Voigt approximation [23]. From the

model of the nanotube/polypropylene nanocomposites the volume fraction is estimated to $\sim 0,025$. A plot of the Voigt approximation is also shown in figure 3.

The moduli of the carbon nanotube, the polypropylene and the nanocomposite systems are shown in table 1 together with the calculated upper bound of the nanotube/polypropylene nanocomposite.

	Carbon nanotube	Polypropylene	Nanocomposte	Voigt app.
Tensile modulus	1050 GPa	6,4 GPa	29 GPa	32 GPa

Table 1: Tensile moduli of the carbon nanotube, the polypropylene and the nanocomposite systems.

The tensile modulus of the single walled carbon nanotube is determined to be approximately 1 TPa and this corresponds well with results obtained by other studies such as the results of Sanchez-Portal et.al. [7]. The value obtained for the modulus of the polypropylene system is fairly large and differ from the experimental value of $\sim 1,0$ GPa – $1,7$ GPa [22]. The difference in the moduli can either be due to the lack of any form of defects in the molecular dynamics model which may be present in the actual polypropylene or be due to a system size that is too small and therefore not representative. The difference between the moduli is however estimated to be acceptable.

For the infinite nanotube/polypropylene nanocomposite the value obtained for the tensile modulus are almost identical with the Voigt approximation which correlates with the theory of composite materials and with the results obtained by Frankland and Brenner [18].

The stress-strain diagram obtained for the finite carbon nanotube/polypropylene composite is plotted in figure 4 along with the results obtained for the polypropylene system.

Figure 4: Stress-strain diagram for the finite carbon nanotube/polypropylene nanocomposite and the polypropylene system.

The two plots in figure 4 are almost identical with no large differences and hence the carbon nanotube has no immediate reinforcing effect on the nanocomposite, at least not for low strains. The length of the finite nanotube used in these simulations was ~ 5 nm and the results in figure 4 indicate that this length is not adequate to obtain a proper load transfer between the carbon nanotube and the amorphous polypropylene matrix.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this study molecular dynamic simulations were applied to determine the behavior of two nanocomposites: an infinite carbon nanotube embedded in an amorphous polypropylene matrix and a finite, capped nanotube embedded in the same matrix. In both of the systems only weak secondary interactions between the nanotube and the matrix were considered.

For the infinite carbon nanotube/polypropylene composite the tensile modulus was shown to be identical to the upper bound of the modulus by use of the Voigt approximation.

For the finite, capped carbon nanotube/polypropylene nanocomposite the length of the nanotube was not adequate to transfer the load from the polypropylene matrix to the nanotube and hence no reinforcing effect was observed.

FUTURE WORK

As mentioned in the introduction the molecular dynamic simulations presented in this paper are preliminary studies of the molecular behavior of a carbon nanotube/polypropylene system. In order to obtain a broader understanding of the behavior of a nanotube embedded in a polypropylene matrix the molecular dynamic simulations should be extended to include the investigation of other aspects. In the present studies only weak secondary interaction between the nanotube and the matrix was considered. However, an obvious continuation of these studies would be to model a system with a varying degree of covalent bonding between the tube and the polypropylene matrix. Thereby the influence of the covalent bonding on the properties of the nanocomposite can be examined. Furthermore, only amorphous polypropylene has been considered in the simulations and since polypropylene can appear both as an amorphous and as a semicrystalline polymer it would be necessary to include modeling of carbon nanotubes in a crystalline polypropylene matrix. A further aspect to be considered is the assembling of nanotubes in bundles. Thess et.al. [24] have shown that single walled carbon nanotubes assemble in bundles and if the nanotubes are not treated chemically or mechanically the tubes will remain in bundles when mixed with a polymer. Since the mechanical properties of the bundles are different from the properties of the individual nanotubes the behavior of a bundle/polypropylene composite will be different from that of an individual nanotube/polypropylene system. Using molecular dynamics the properties and the behavior of a bundle/polymer composite system could be examined.

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